

Experience of Peer Bullying and Health Impacts of Peer Victimization among Adolescence Students

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Abstract

The study was conducted to assess the experience of peer bullying among secondary level students and specifically to find out the prevalence of peer bullying, impacts of peer victimization identify association between prevalence and selected variables. A cross sectional descriptive study includes total number of 100 secondary level students. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was adopted. The semi-structured questionnaire were self-administered. The data was analysed using descriptive and inferential like frequency, distribution and percentage tables. Result: The study revealed that 21% of the students were involved in peer bullying. Among them, 14% were victimized (who are bullied) and 7% were perpetrators (who bully others). 45.6% of victimized student experienced of different health impacts including 37.87% of psychological, 33.17% of social impact and 28.96% of physical impacts. The study explained that there is no any statistical association between prevalence of peer bullying and socio demographic variables at $p < 0.05$ level. Hence, research hypothesis (H_1) was rejected and null hypothesis (H_0) was accepted. The study reported involvement of the students in peer bullying. About half of the victimized student experienced different forms of health impacts. The research concluded with the information that sensitize the need for awareness about peer bullying among students, teachers and parents.

Introduction

Adolescence is a period in human development characterized by transition. One of the most important transitions occurring during adolescence is the rise of peer relationships in importance and influence. Peer relationships provide a context not only for the acquisition and maintenance of friendships and friendship networks but also for the development of key social skills, social problem solving skills, and empathy [1].

Teens are influenced every day by their peers. In fact, every time your tween or teen spends time with their peers, they are being influenced. Sometimes peer influences can be positive like encouraging each other to try new things or step out of their comfort zone in a positive way. But peer pressure also can be negative, especially when it relates to drugs, alcohol use, and even bullying [2].

Bullying is defined as trying to gain power via aggression and aiming to repeatedly pulling the victim down socially, emotionally and physically. Bullying is a widespread problem in schools. Taunting, teasing, and fighting don't constitute bullying when two persons are approximately the same physical or psychological strength [3]. The term originally was adopted to describe aggression among school children, as early research focused on groups of children attacking individuals. However, later, researcher acknowledged that one-on-one bullying was actually more common [4].

Bullies regularly involves hurting, teasing, name calling, or intimidation, particularly against those who are smaller or less able to defend themselves. They believe they are superior to other students, or blame others for being weak or different. Bullies engages frequently fight with others as a way to assert dominance and may also enlist friends to bully for them. Bullying might be

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physical, verbal, relational, or electronic (cyberbullying) [5].

Peer bullying causes many negative occurrences from short-term happiness and depression to death. Studies, which investigated bullying behaviors in terms of developmental and socio-bullying has many negative effects on children who bully and children who are the victims of bullying with respect to physical, psychological, social and educational matters [6].

Peer victimization is the experience among children of being a target of the aggressive behavior of other children, who are not siblings and not necessarily age-mates [7]. Traditionally, peer victimization is identified mainly on the physical acts of aggression like kicking, punching and slapping [8].

The victim of peer bullying are more likely to exhibit increased depression, anxiety, posttraumatic stress, alcohol use, drug abuse, isolation etc. students. They are more likely to high school are more likely to engage in anti-social activity. Peer bullying behavior has also been linked to other forms of antisocial behavior like vandalism, shoplifting, skipping, and dropping out of schools, fighting, murders, suicide [9].

Although peer victimization has previously been considered an inevitable childhood occurrence, parents, school personnel, and health professionals have recognized the impact of being victimized on a range of psychosocial adjustment problems. Policy changes within schools have lagged, resulting in few improvements in the situation [10].

Methods

Research Design

Quantitative research approach was used in the study following a descriptive research design to assess the experience of peer bullying and impact of peer victimization.

Study Population and Sampling

Literature showed adolescent students are more engaged in bullying, 133 students studying in grade 8,9,10 of sunshine Public School Bangalore were selected as target sample. Non probability purposive sampling technique was adopted using Slovan’s formula, $n = N / (1 + Ne2)$ which results 99.81 that is approximately 100.

Development of the Tools

The tool is developed by slightly modifying the highly referenced tool by Swedish- Norwegian psychologist DR. Dan Owleus who is considered pioneer in bullying research. The Owleus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (OBVQ) is one of the most widely used instrument to measure the prevalence, experience and impact of peer bullying.

Description of the Tool

Section A: consists of demographic data

Section B: consists of questions related to experience of peer bullying

Section c: consists of list of question related to impacts of peer victimization

Interpretation of Scores

Consisting of likert scale with point values are assigned as: Never=1 rarely =2 Sometimes=3 Often times=4 Always=5

Scale scores are computed by summing item responses. Scores on each of the subscales have a possible range of 15 to 75. Higher score reflect more health impact.

Validity and Reliability

Content validity of the tool was established through literature review and obtaining the suggestion from 3 experts in the field of community health nursing department, statistician and English language experts. Cronbach’s alpha test was used to test reliability which result the sum of item variance of 2.97, variance total score 11.21 and cronbach’s alpha`α`value was 0.8

Data Collection and Analysis

The main study data collection was done from 16/06/2022 to 21/06/2022

The obtained data was planned to analyses on the basis of objective of the study using the descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Description of socio-demographic variables

Figure 1: Age of School Children

The above figure illustrate that as per age, majority of the sample that is 31(31%) were 12years of age, 24(24%) were 13years, 26(26%) were 14 years and 19(19%) were of 15years.

Figure 2: Gender

The above figure reveals that as per gender, more than half of sample that is 54(54%) were male and 46(46%) were female.

Figure 4: Religion

The above figure elicits, majority of the students that is 65(65%) belongs to Hindu religion, 26(26%) to Muslim, 7(7%) were Christian and only 2(2%) to others religion.

Figure 3: Grade

The figure reveals about half of the respondents that is 48(48%) were in class 8, 29(29%) were in class 9 whereas 23(23%) were studying in class 10.

Figure 5: Types of Family

As per types of family, majority of them that is 61(61%) were from nuclear family, 25(25%) were from joint family whereas 14(14%) were from extended family.

Table 1: Prevalence of Peer Bullying

Sl. No	Victimization		Bullying perpetration		Not involved	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1.	14	14%	7	7%	79	79%

The above table shows that the overall prevalence of any bullying behavior was 21%.Among them

victimization was 14%, and only bullying perpetration was 7%.

Table 2: Forms and Frequencies of Peer Bullying

Forms of bullying behavior		
Victimization	Frequency	Percentage
Verbal victimization	42	42%
Physical victimization	18	18%
Social victimization	10	10%
Attack on property victimization	3	3%
Sexual victimization	7	7%
Cyber victimization	20	20%
Bullying perpetration		
Bullying	Frequency	Percentage
Verbal bullying	48	48%
Physical bullying	10	10%
Social bullying	14	14%
Attack on property bullying	2	2%
Sexual bullying	4	4%
Cyber bullying	22	22%

The result revealed, majority (41%) of the students are verbally, 18%physically, 20% cyber, 10%socially, 7% sexually victimized and 3%had their property attacked. Similarly, in case of Perpetration, the result showed

about half of the students bully their friends verbally, 10% physically, 22% through social media, 14% socially, 4% sexually whereas 2% attacked the property.

Table 3: Association of Socio-Demographic Variables with Peer Bullying Behavior

Sl No.	Variables	Bullying behavior							Chi square	p-Value
		Victimization		Bullying		Not involved		Total		
		f	%	f	%	f	%			
1	Age group								2.760 df=6	0.838 NS
	12 years	5	35.7	3	42.8	23	29.1	31		
	13 years	4	28.6	1	14.3	19	24.1	24		
	14 years	4	28.6	1	14.3	21	26.6	26		
	15 years	1	7.1	2	28.6	16	20.3	19		
	Total	14	100	7	100	79	100	100		
2	Gender								0.765 df=2	0.682 NS
	18-19Years	9	64.3	4	57.1	41	51.9	54		
	20-21 Years	5	35.7	3	42.9	38	48.1	46		
	Total	14	100	7	100	79	100	100		
3	Grade								2.802 df=4	0.588 NS
	8-class	6	42.9	2	28.6	40	50.6	48		
	9-calss	3	21.4	3	42.9	23	29.1	29		
	10-calss	5	35.7	2	28.6	16	20.3	23		
	Total	14	100	7	100	79	100	100		
4	Religion								2.800 df=6	0.834 NS
	Hindu	9	64.3	4	57.1	52	65.8	65		
	Muslim	5	37.7	2	28.6	19	24.1	26		
	Christian	0	0	1	14.3	6	7.6	7		
	Others	0	0	0	0	2	2.5	2		
	Total	14	100	7	100	79	100	100		
5	Type of family								3.330 df=4	0.504 NS
	Nuclear	8	57.1	4	57.1	49	62	61		
	Joint	2	14.3	2	28.6	21	26.6	25		
	Extended	4	28.6	1	14.3	9	11.4	14		
	Total	14	100	7	100	79	100	100		

The above table demonstrates the association between prevalence of peer bullying and selected demographic variables of the participants. Demographic variables

like Age, sex education, type of family didn't show any significant association with prevalence of peer bullying at $p < 0.05$ level.

Figure 6: Health Impacts of Peer Bullying among School Children

Interpreting those impact percentage by summing the responses, the study results 37.87% psychological impacts, 33.17% social impact and 28.96% physical impact among peer victimized students.

Implication

Nursing Education

Nursing curriculum should include awareness on peer bullying, its types or forms and health consequences and preventable as well as remedial actions.

Nursing Practice

Nurse in the clinical and community area have a crucial role in observing prevalence of peer bullying. Nurse must educate the school children, their and teachers regarding the impact peer bullying and plan some remedial actions.

Nursing Research

The finding of this study will be used as base line data in the future for further conduction of research on similar topic. The finding may be utilized by the emerging researchers for their reference purpose. The results can also be compared with another research in respective with time interval, different age group of different study area.

Nursing Administration

The nurse administrator should conduct in-service education to disseminate the research findings through continuous nursing education to all nurses. And also conferences, workshop and symposium based on the peer bullying and its impact on health.

Limitations

Although the study includes important topic including prevalence, types and health impacts of peer bullying, it has some shortcomings. The study is limited to 100 school students and assess only quantitative responses. Further assessment regarding not only prevalence but also preventive measures of peer bullying would be more effective investing more time and effort.

Discussion

In this study, total 21% of the students were involved in peer bullying. Among them, 17% were victim, who were bullied by their friends and 4% were perpetrator who bullied their friends. Similar study conducted in turkey obtained from 1670 students in the 9th and 10th grades Peer Bullying Scale 17% of the students were in a bullying cycle (5.3% as bully, 5.9% as victim, and 5.8% as both bully and victim).

The study revealed, majority of the students are verbally bullied followed by physical and cyber bullying. In case of Perpetration, the result showed, about half of the students bully their friends verbally. Similar kind of study conducted in 2 urban schools in Bangalore revealed that Verbal bullying and verbal victimization was the most prevalent with physical bullying and cyber bullying.

However there are many literature review demonstrating association of socio-demographic variables and bullying behavior.

There are also some studies reported no significant

relation supporting result of the present study like a cross sectional study in Kuwait children showed there was no any significant relation in prevalence of bullying and family type, gender.

Interpreting those impact percentage, the study results 37.87% psychological impacts, 33.17% social impact and 28.96% physical impact. Corresponding to the result, a longitudinal study conducted by National Center for Educational Statistics in US school students indicate that bullying has a negative effect on mental health (27%), social impact (19%), their school work (19%), and physical health (14%).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Schools should put in place thorough anti-bullying programs that foster empathy and knowledge in order to successfully combat peer bullying and the negative effects it has on teenagers' health. Establishing secure reporting routes for victims is vital, along with giving access to mental health treatment. Participating in workshops with parents and community people can improve awareness and preventative initiatives. Fostering peer support programs can help students develop an allyship culture. It will be easier to customize interventions if bullying prevalence and effects are routinely assessed. Last but not least, teaching pupils coping mechanisms and resilience would enable them to overcome the difficulties posed by peer victimization and enhance their general wellbeing.

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